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2.GENERAL INFORMATION

RESEARCHERS

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Is the principal investigator a health professional according to the Law of 10 May 2015? nee

Other KU Leuven researchers:

Olivier Lemeire
Pei-Shan Chi
Leander Vignero
Stijn Conix

FUNDING

Is the research funded (e.g. in the context of a research project/contract/mandate)? ja

FWO mandaat

Department responsible for contracts concluded or to be concluded:

LEADING ETHICAL COMMITTEE

The leading ethical committee in this research project: SMEC

3.RESEARCH

TITLE, DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVES

Unique and full title of the research project/protocol:

Comparing the societal relevance of different Humanities disciplines through peer review: follow-up study

Description of the research project/protocol :

There is an increasing demand, both from funding agencies and societal stakeholders, that academic research should be societally relevant. At the same time, much research, particularly in the humanities, gets criticized for lacking societal relevance. This raises the question whether, and to what extent, there are differences between various disciplines in the humanities with respect to societal relevance. This study aims to compare the societal relevance of different disciplines in the humanities. We propose to use two methods for this:

- 1) Compare various altmetrics of journal articles and books published in these disciplines between 2015 and 2020.
- 2) Use expert judgement to evaluate the societal relevance of these same books and journal papers (on the basis of their abstract). This method builds on a previously published pilot-study and a recently completed pilot with the same methodology. In addition, it builds on the fact that funding agencies commonly assume that researchers can evaluate the societal relevance of academic research, and use such relevance as one of the main criteria for distributing funding (in peer review).

The objectives of the research (project):

This is a study that replicates a recently completed pilot study that was approved by SMEC last year (G-2022-5233-R3(AMD)). Like the study it replicates, it has a triple aim:

- 1) compare the societal relevance of different humanities disciplines
- 2) test whether expert judgement-based methods for evaluating societal relevance are valuable
- 3) test whether altmetric-based measures and expert judgement based measures converge

Ultimately, the aim of this research is to contribute towards the broader aim of tracking and increasing the societal relevance of academic research.

ETHICAL JUSTIFICATION

Description ethical justification:

The ethical costs of this research are limited: we will pay PhD-students and PhD-holders to rate paper and book abstracts according to a range of criteria. Participation is thus voluntary, and while they will lose some time doing it, they will be paid for that time. We will only collect the personal data that is strictly necessary for running the study (name, whether the person holds a PhD in a humanities field (and which field), whether the person identifies as WEIRD, and the gender of that person). Only anonymized data will be made public and all identifying data will be deleted. On the other hand, the ethical benefits are substantial: we contribute to the broad project of tracking the societal impact of research, and using such tracking mechanisms for making academic research more impactful and relevant (e.g. by identifying kinds of research that tend to have more impact)

Potential disadvantages/risks and advantages/contributions of the research on both the individual level (e.g., the risk that COVID-19 is transmitted to a participant):

RESEARCH TECHNIQUES, INSTRUMENTS & EQUIPMENT

Questionnaire: ja

Non-validated questionnaire: ja

No attachment available: The survey is difficult to upload because it contains abstracts randomly drawn from a large set of Web of Science abstracts, which will only be randomly selected once the study preregistration is published (and this preregistration requires the SMEC application to be finished). The survey will have the following structure and questions: - It starts with a landing page with an informed consent form and instructions (attached to this application) - the landing page is followed by 33 sets of 5 abstracts (one for each Humanities field) randomly drawn from the complete set of Web Of Science abstracts. With each set of 5 abstracts, participants get the following instructions: "Rank the abstracts according to how likely they will be funded by the ideal committee, with the one most likely to be funded at the top and the one least likely to be funded at the bottom. If the ranking should remain as it is, please change and then restore the order of one abstract so the software knows that the abstracts have been ranked. When you are done ranking the abstracts, decide for each abstract whether you think it would be funded by the ideal committee. Indicate this by putting a '1' (i.e. yes, it would be funded), or a '0' (i.e. no, it would not be funded) in the open text field after each abstract. Keep in mind that if an abstract gets a '0', all abstracts below that should have a '0' as well. Similarly, if an abstract gets a '1', all abstracts above that should get a '1' as well."

RESEARCH METHOD

Methodologies and practical procedures:

Paid raters (PhD students) will get 33 sets of 5 abstracts, and will be asked to respond to one question for each abstract and one questions for each set of abstracts (see above). No demographic information will be collected, except for:

- whether they are humanities scholars, and the home discipline (broadly constructed: literature, linguistics, philosophy/theology, architecture, art/design, history) if they are.

- Their gender

- whether they identify as WEIRD (i.e. western, educated, industrialized, rich, democratic)

We collect gender and WEIRD-status because it is suggested in the literature that these might impact judgements in peer review. Even in combination with the field of specialization, these pieces of personal information would not allow identification of the raters. Again, all identifying data is deleted and only anonymized data will be made public.

We will ensure that we have at least 1 from each humanities field and 10 humanities scholars at most, and at least 5 non-humanities scholars (max. 10). Raters will be briefed about the methods through the invitation ad, and a 20-min video explaining the task prior to rating. In addition, they will be invited explicitly to ask questions by email or request a video-call if they have further questions or doubts. Raters will be recruited through Upwork (<https://www.upwork.com/>), a well-known platform for hiring freelance workers, and will be paid \$20 per hour (4.5 hrs total) for their work. The statistical methods to analyze these results will be described in the preregistration.

Aspects of the research that would impact stricter measures around COVID-19:

This research will not be affected by COVID19, as the recruitment and survey place online.

EXPECTED START DATE AND END DATE

The expected start date of contacting participants (e.g. for data collection, recruitment) for the experiment/study (should be in the future) as well as the end date for participants.:

StartDate: The study will start as soon as ethical approval is given by SMEC.

EndDate: 31/10/2023

4.COLLECTING AND SHARING PERSONAL DATA USED IN THE PROJECT / STUDY

PRIMARY/SECONDARY DATA PROCESSING

Do you intend to collect new data (primary processing) or do you use previously collected data (secondary processing)?

Primary processing: ja

Secondary processing: nee

EXTERNAL PARTNERS

Other not KU Leuven researchers:

Li Lin

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It is a non-commercial study.

Is another university, research institution or other partner involved in this research project? nee

ROLES OF THE PARTIES INVOLVED

Who determines the objectives and resources of the research?

This is determined within KU Leuven.

Is there an external partner involved who will process personal data (e.g. collection of data, analyzing the data) as a data processor on behalf of KU Leuven (alone or with other partners)? nee

SHARING, IMPORT AND EXPORT OF DATA

Will the data be transferred to/ shared with persons/agencies outside KU Leuven? nee

PLACE DATA PROCESSING

Where will you process the data?

Belgium: ja

5. PARTICIPANTS/DATA SUBJECTS AND CATEGORIES OF DATA

CATEGORIES OF DATA SUBJECTS

Personal data you will use or process in your research:

We do not process personal data, apart from:

- a list of names of raters.
- their broad field of specialization (philosophy, religion, history, literature, linguistics, non-humanities)
- Their gender
- whether they identify as WEIRD

These are not selected from a larger list that we know of, as we will recruit through an ad on Upwork, and freelance workers that are interested will have to contact us to participate.

Note that the names will only be processed by one member of the team (Stijn Conix), who will assign a random code to each rater and will remove the names immediately after collecting the data. The other members of the team will thus only get the random codes, gender, field and weird-status. These data will not allow the other team members to identify the raters.

Are vulnerable people involved? nee

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Only PhD students and PhD holders (PhD obtained in 2018 or after that) active on the third party platform (Upwork) are eligible for participation.

CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA

What categories of data do you intend to collect or use?

Ordinary personal data: ja

- Identification information (e.g. names, (email) addresses)
- Personal details (e.g. age, gender)
- Education and training

Identificatiegegevens: namen

Persoonlijke kenmerken: geslacht / gender(identiteit)

SCALE OF THE PROCESSING

What is the expected number of participants whose personal data will be collected?

We will hire:

- At least 5 humanities scholars (one from each field), and at most 10.
- at least 5 non-humanities scholars, and at most 10.

Hence, we expect to hire between 10 and 20 participants.

How does this sample relate to the relevant population?

The relevant population is unknown, as it concerns all scholars in the world.

How many data do you process from one participant and how diverse are these data?

discipline, educational attainment, name, weird-status, gender

What is the geographical scope of the personal data that you process?

Global

RECRUITMENT, REMUNERATION AND BENEFITS

Who will recruit the participants, how, where and by whom the participants will be approached for inclusion and obtainment of informed consent.:

We will recruit raters through a third party platform (Upwork), and ask them to contact us in case they are interested. We will provide all the necessary information regarding privacy, remuneration and other procedures through said platform. This will include how we will process the data.

Recruitment is done with a poster or flyer, add as an attachment:

Upwork ad.docx
14,26 KB

Will participants receive a remuneration or compensation for their participation? ja

Cost reimbursement (i.e., food, drinks, transport, parking): nee

Additional compensation (e.g., voucher, course credits, money): ja

Raters will get a fixed sum of 100 USD.

Are there other benefits by participating in this project? (e.g., what can a participant learn from the study) ja

Raters may feel motivated to reflect about the societal relevance of their research. Raters will also be invited to an optional meeting in which we present the results once they are published.

RISKS, DISCOMFORT AND COUNSELING

Describe possible risks or whether participants might experience (physical or mental) discomfort, embarrassment, confusion, etc. during the course of the study:

There are no risks connected to working as a rater for this study. We will of course emphasize that if at any point during the work the raters do feel uncomfortable, they should not hesitate to let us know they no longer wish to participate.

Is any support or counseling offered after participation?

We do not offer counselling.

6. TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES FOR DATA PROCESSING AND DATA MANAGEMENT

RETENTION OF DATA

Where will digital and audiovisual data be stored?

OneDrive linked to a KU Leuven account

Where will paper data be stored?

There are no paper data (for example also informed consent will be asked digitally).

Who will have access to participants' (personal) data during the study?

The involved KU Leuven researchers. (cfr page 2)

Who will have access to participants' (personal) data after the study?

Others, please specify...

Only one KU Leuven researcher will have access to the personal data during the study (Stijn Conix). We will publish all data on a public repository once the study is finished. However, no personal data will be published. The personal data (i.e. list of names) will be deleted as soon as data has been collected. Participants cannot be identified through their gender, field and WEIRD-status.

For how long will the (personal) data be stored after the study?

Different, please specify (for example because the study is longitudinal or because the data will be archived in the context of historic research):

The personal data will be deleted once the other data has been collected. The other data will be published on a public repository.

ANONYMISATION/PSEUDONYMISATION

Do you plan to anonymise or pseudonymise the data at some point in the research process?

Not anonymised or not pseudonymised data: nee

You will anonymise personal data yourself: ja

The personal data will be deleted once the other data has been collected.

OTHER ORGANISATIONAL AND TECHNICAL SECURITY MEASURES

Will you take any other measures to protect the privacy of data subjects?

no

7. INFORMING DATA SUBJECTS/PARTICIPANTS

RESEARCH THAT IMPLIES DECEPTION

Will participants be deceived? nee

INFORMING DATA SUBJECTS/PARTICIPANTS

Will the necessary information be provided to the data subjects/participants or is this already done?

In case of primary processing: ja

 landing page11-10.docx
15,28 KB

PROCEDURE FOR INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE STUDY

Describe your procedure for informed consent for participation in the study in detail:

Participants will have to watch a 20-minute information video that explains the rating-instructions that are also summarized in the attached landing page. They will have to agree to the attached informed consent before they start the rating work in Qualtrics.

 landing page11-10.docx
15,28 KB

DEBRIEFING

Which information is given to participants during debriefing and how will this be provided

We will organize an optional meeting after the study to present all results to the raters, and to give them the opportunity to give feedback and share their experiences.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE STUDY RESULTS

Which information is given to participants about the outcome of the study? Will participants receive their individual results or only the overall study results? How will this information be provided?

Raters will not get their individual results, but will have access to the aggregated data.

8. RIGHTS OF DATA SUBJECTS AND LAWFULNESS OF THE PROCESSING

RIGHTS OF DATA SUBJECTS

Would your research be seriously impaired if data subjects wish to exercise their right to request access, rectification, restriction of processing and right to object to processing?

nee

LAWFULNESS OF PROCESSING

Selected legal basis:

University research is usually conducted in the public interest: ja

9. RISK ANALYSIS BY THE RESEARCHER

Does the research involve a high privacy risk for the data subjects?

If the data were to be made public, would this have a significant impact on the data subjects? nee

Do you plan to use special category data? nee

Do you plan to process personal data of vulnerable groups? nee

Will large-scale processing be carried out? In your answer, do not only consider absolute numbers, but also the sample size relative to the relevant population.(see question 4)? nee

Will the data be transferred to a non-EU country that is not on the 'white list'? nee

Do you plan to link different (special categories of) personal data? nee

Will the processing have legal consequences or a similar impact, such as exclusion or discrimination, on the data subject? nee

Will the processing prevent the data subject from exercising his/her rights, or from using a service or contract? nee

Will you systematically monitor people in public places? nee

Will the data be processed to create profiles of individuals and to make predictions? nee

Will you make innovative use of technological applications such as a combination of fingerprint and facial recognition for access control? nee

Do you plan to use non-pseudonymised personal data? nee